

PROTECTION OF FLORA AND FAUNA

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ABSTRACT

The loss or decline of any plant or animal species will cause inconvenience to the population of different species, because species are always interconnected in different ways. In the article, the authors made comments about the preservation of flora and fauna.

No one can say with clear evidence why the dinosaurs went extinct. One thing is certain, human activity and impact on nature came after the dinosaurs. Today is a different life. The number of endangered species is increasing. From 1980 to 2000, about 40 species of plants and animals became extinct in the United States. The reason is that the number of species is decreasing due to the fact that mankind occupies large areas of the earth and uses it to satisfy its needs. The loss or decline of any one species is detrimental to the populations of different species, since species are always interrelated in different ways. Conservation of species diversity in aquatic ecosystems and terrestrial ecosystems remains one of the urgent problems of today. As a result of our unwise use of natural resources, many species and non-living components are endangered. It is the duty of each of us as a human being to preserve the biosphere, which is distinguished by its beautiful

scenery, beautiful corners, and the uniqueness of its animal and plant world. Biodiversity High biodiversity is found in tropical forests, i.e. areas with permanent salinity, including the Yasuni National Park in Ecuador. Land biodiversity is 25 times higher than ocean biodiversity. Of the 8.7 million species that exist on Earth, 2.1 million are estimated to be unique to the ocean. Colombia is considered a country with high biodiversity, there are many endemic species. That is, these types are not found in any other country. Colombia is home to 10% of all species on earth and more than 1,900 species of birds, more than in Europe and North America. Colombia is home to 10% of the world's mammal species. Although species are protected by law, they cannot survive unless their natural environment is preserved. Environmental protection is often based on the preservation of the natural environment or the entire ecosystem. One way to do this is to create

nature reserves, such as international parks and wildlife areas. In 1872, the first international park, Yellow Stone National Park, was established in the United States. At that time, the grizzly bear, moose and deer were moved and relocated to the North American territory. These animals roamed many parts of the earth to gather food. If their natural habitat is small, they cannot survive. For example, a grizzly bear needs a large amount of food per day. A grizzly bear needs several hundred km of territory to feed itself. Without national parks and wildlife areas, some animals would be far less abundant than they are today. Plants are the primary source of life on Earth. They are 380 billion per year. tons of organic matter, of which 325 billion. t. to sea and ocean plants, 38 bln. t. to forests, 6 bln. tons corresponds to meadows. Also, if there was no photosynthesis process due to plants, i.e. green plants, the amount of carbon (CO₂) in the air would increase and people and animals would die. However, the same CO₂ gas coming from the water surface and soil in the atmosphere is absorbed by plants, and as a result of photosynthesis, green plants release oxygen to the environment. Plants are natural sources of food, fodder, medicine, clothing and many other substances for humans. Medicinal plants that are widely used by our people are used. Examples of these are incense, Ermon, chakanda, aloe, namatak, gazanda and others. Plants are of great importance in the treatment of various infectious diseases in the human body. Humans also use plants extensively as fodder for livestock. In Uzbekistan, the cotton plant is considered the main raw material, and it is used for various purposes. Humans also use plants as building materials. One of the

important aspects of plants in human life is the greening of the environment, including maple, poplar, oak, coniferous evergreen plants. In addition, they clean the dust in the air and enrich it with oxygen. Forest plants occupy a special place in the rational use and protection of the plant world. Forests in the republic constitute a single state forest fund. The forests of Uzbekistan are divided into mountain, desert, grove and valley forests by their characteristics. At the beginning of the 20th century, the area of Uzbekistan's forests decreased by 4-5 times. Especially forest forests have faced anthropogenic degradation. The state of forests around the world is not satisfactory. Excessive deforestation is rampant and their restoration is insufficient. The annual volume of deforestation is 3 billion m³. It increased 1.5 times by 2000, according to the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). The state of tropical forests (7% of the Earth's surface) is particularly worrying. According to accurate scientific sources, forests made up 47% of the area of the earth where we live 1,500 years ago, and now they make up 27%. As a result of the pursuit of profit in industrial sources in many countries, a lot of forests have been cut down, and large factories and factories are being built in their place. As a result of the pollution of the environment, many rare and rare plant species are dying. According to the official information of the UN, it is noted that 250,000 different plant species will disappear from the period when the industry began to develop. After gaining independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the protection of the environment, fauna and flora. On December 9, 1992, the laws

on "Nature Protection", on May 7, 1993, on "Specially Protected Areas", and finally on December 26, 1997, on "Protection of the flora and its rational use" were adopted. These laws deal with relations in the field of protection and use of the world of plants growing in natural conditions, as well as wild plants cultivated for reproduction and preservation of genetic stock. Article 2 - The main tasks of legislation on relations in the field of flora protection and use are as follows: - To preserve the species composition and genetic fund of flora in natural conditions. Maintaining the integrity of natural plant communities and habitats where wild plants grow. - Ensuring rational use of flora and its reproduction, legal regulation of activities of legal entities and individuals in the field of flora protection and use. Article 4 - State management in the field of protection and use of flora. Government bodies of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as specially authorized state bodies and state bodies are management bodies. Legal entities and individuals must cover the flora in the manner and under the conditions specified in the legal documents on the protection and use of the flora. These laws are important documents for the preservation, conservation and protection of all plant species. There are about 4.5 thousand plant species in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among them are many rare, endemic and relict species that need serious protection. The number of such species is 301 and included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. With the honor of our independence, a lot of work has been done on such plants that need protection. The number of such species is about 400, and they make up 10-

12% of the flora of Uzbekistan. The wrong attitude of the population to nature is also the reason for the decrease of plants. Especially in recent years, we have witnessed the decline of red tulips, sallagul, syrach and similar elegant flowering plants. The "Red Book" of Uzbekistan was established in 1979 for the preservation and protection of plant species. Red is a dangerous, forbidding and symbolic symbol. "Red book" provides excellent information about rare and endangered species of flora. Its mission is to involve the public and state agencies in the issue of nature protection and to help preserve the gene pool of species. 163 endangered species of the flora of Uzbekistan were included in the 1984 edition of the Red Book. It should be remembered that the first volume (top) of the "Red Book" was on animals and was published in 1983. By 1998, the number of plant species included in the "Red Book" of Uzbekistan reached 301. 321 plants and 3 types of fungi were included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan published in 2009. It is possible to have positive results only if the general public participates in the process of plant protection. Only then, we will preserve the priceless wealth of the flora for future generations. The endangered desert tortoise's future is uncertain. Human development is causing the desert tortoise's habitat to shrink in the southwestern United States. Southern sea otter: The sea otter lives in the shallow waters of the Pacific Ocean in the US. For centuries, sea otters have been hunted for their unique fur. Pelicans are birds adapted to eat fish and aquatic plants. In the middle of the 20th century, the use of the drug DDT became widespread. In 1972, the drug DDT began to be widely used in the United

States as a control for the destruction of insects that destroy agricultural crops. This situation led to the decline of pelicans. Because the eggs of pelicans have become thinner. Also, early hatching of palapon occurred. Brown pelicans have completely disappeared from Louisiana and Texas. As of 2000, there are more than 7,000 brown pelicans living in Louisiana and Texas. Animals are an integral part of biological resources and they play an important role in the exchange of substances and energy in nature. The animal world is very important in the life and activity of mankind in general. It is known that domesticated animals such as cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, horses, donkeys, camels, dogs and cats are kept for a specific purpose in our lives. Some species of animals are a source of protein, oil, and milk for us, while others are useful for the economy, as transport, guarding houses, and fighting pests. Wild animals also have their own useful properties, including fur, medicine, food, and wool. Animals of the main economic importance in Uzbekistan are: water swimmers, saigas, muskrats, turtles, poisonous snakes, cockroaches, mountain goats and invertebrates. Animals serve to maintain the balance of natural means in nature. In general, there are many types of animals, there are more than one and a half million of them. If we consider 100% of the energy received by plants from the sun, then 50% of the remaining energy is absorbed by plants during respiration, and the organic matter passes to herbivores and carnivores. Animals, especially earthworms, ants, termites, vertebrate earth diggers, etc., are of great importance in improving soil composition and increasing its productivity. These animals soften the soil, mix it, fertilize it with feces

and plant residues. Animals are also involved in pollination of plants, distribution of seeds and fruits. Some birds of prey kill pests (rodents) and increase plant productivity, or some insects protect plants from pests and diseases. For example, one owl destroys 1,000 mice and saves 0.5 tons of grain in a year, and ants protect forests from diseases. If sedimentary rocks (chalk, limestone) are formed from the remains of single-celled marine animals, coral islands are formed in the shallow and warm water part of the oceans due to the activity of polyps. Both in ancient times and now, with the development of technology, people were interested in animals for their beautiful skin, tasty meat, and valuable bones, but very ignorant people learned how to hunt and destroyed the animal world. It is known from the sources that between 1872 and 1874, during the construction of the Kansas railroad in the USA, "enthusiastic" hunters annually hunted 2.5 million deer. those who shot the bison were probably not interested in the tasty meat or skin of this harmless animal. As a result, bison have decreased so much that now only a few of them are preserved in special reserves. There are many types of animal world of Uzbekistan and they are colorful. There are more than 650 specimens of vertebrate animals in our territory, including 83 species of fish, 3 amphibian species, 58 species of reptiles, more than 424 species of birds and 97 species of mammals. When talking about the protection of the animal world, it is necessary to pay special attention to the decreasing number of aquatic animals. Because, especially among them, the decline of fish species is a matter of concern. The reason for this is the pollution

of water bodies, the increase in the weight of water in some places can be a big loss for certain types of fish. In addition, poachers are also causing the decline of fish. The area of fishing farms in our country is 38 million hectares. The Turanian tiger and the red wolf have completely disappeared from the territory of the country, and there is a danger of extinction of such creatures as the leopard, the Old Asian leopard, the striped hyena, and the tuvalok. According to the data, Mirzachol, Karshi desert, Surkhan-Sherabad desert, central parts of Fergana valley have been developed in the territory of Uzbekistan. This is the reason for the decline of a number of animals living in the desert environment, including rare species such as gazelle and beautiful

tulovak. A number of beautiful animals, including the mountain sheep, the Iranian otter, the Central Asian capchailo, have been completely decimated by ignorant hunters. In the protection of rare and endangered species of animals, it is necessary to create favorable opportunities for their reproduction and improvement of their living conditions. For this, it is necessary, firstly, to strictly control endangered and rare animal species, to completely prevent hunting, and secondly, to preserve the areas where these animals live in their natural state and turn them into reserves and reservations. 80 species of invertebrates belonging to different systematic groups are included.

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